

CONCRETE COLUMNS WRAPPED BY GLASS FIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: With many structural deficiencies in bridges and off-shore structures and increasingly crumbling infrastructure elements, the needs for rehabilitation of infrastructure become critical. In this study, E-glass woven roving (WR), combined with chopped strand mat (CSM), glass fibre tape (GFT) and a vinyl-ester resin, was used to reinforce concrete columns with a wrapping procedure. The results indicate that a great reinforcing efficiency can be obtained. Finite element analysis was performed to analyse the mechanical responses of the composite wrapped concrete columns and to identify the effect of composite properties on the reinforcement efficiency.

KEYWORDS: concrete columns, wrapping technique, glass fibre composite, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

There is a worldwide critical need for rehabilitation of infrastructure because of aging, deterioration, misuse, lack of timely repair and maintenance, and use of improper materials and/or techniques in original construction. Especially, deterioration has been caused by a variety of factors including corrosion due to marine environments, high chloride content in the air and the use of de-icing salts. A widely used technique for concrete structures where retrofit is needed was the use of steel jackets placed around existing columns[1-2]. The use of steel encasement to provide lateral the confinement to concrete in compression has been studied extensively[3-4], which has shown to be able to significantly increase the compression load-carrying capacity and ductility of columns. However, the disadvantages of steel jacketing are corrosion and difficulties associated with the proper placement of steel jackets.

In last a few years, due to high specific strength/stiffness, design placement flexibility and resistance to corrosion, the application of polymer composites in rehabilitation of concrete structures become very attractive. Without reducing the original load-carrying capacity of the structure, the best strengthening performance can be achieved when the constituent materials and composite architecture are optimised to the specific application.

It was found that the winding of a carbon fibre/epoxy composite around square concrete columns can increase the load-carrying capacity of 8-22%, being dependent on the amount of fibres used and the treatment of the substrate[5]. The use of a novel resin infusion technique was shown to contribute to substantial improvements in composite wrap efficiency, and the use of woven glass roving as the reinforcement in the composite wraps was found to substantially increase both load-carrying capacity and deformation capability of the concrete stubs[2]. Furthermore, through the use

of glass/carbon hybrids with a epoxy resin, replication of the initial performance of concrete stubs subjected to deterioration was shown possible, with a simultaneous improvement in load-carrying capacity[6]. The effects of orientation and thickness of the composite wraps on the load-carrying efficiency and ductility of the structural concrete elements have been investigated, and it was found that the predominant use of reinforcements in the hoop direction would enable a high reinforcing efficiency[6].

The rehabilitation of deteriorated infrastructures using composites would use not only carbon fibres and epoxy resin but also glass fibres or the hybrid of carbon/glass fibres and other polymer resins such as vinyl-ester resins. Furthermore, the optimised composite architectures with a proper processing method and a compatible low cost would be an essential task of development of repairing and strengthening techniques. In this study, a E-glass/vinyl-ester resin composite jacket was introduced and effects of composite wrapping architecture were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Composite Architecture

The composite wrap consists of three basic architectures, shown in Figure 1, namely glass chopped strand mat (CSM), woven roving (WR), glass fibre tape (GFT). In some cases, CSM and WR are sandwiched between each other to produce better interplay adhesion of woven roving cloth layers. Meanwhile, WR is a multi-directional reinforcement with $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ angle, which provides the equivalent strength in both axial and hoop directions and plays a basic reinforcing role. GFT in the hoop direction gives very good confinement and an enhanced structural integrity capacity in the hoop direction, being used as the last layers of the jacket; the tape wraps can also reduce the thickness of the composite jacket a little bit, "tightening up" the whole jacket. The tap wraps were wound using helical winding with an angle of 20° . The selection of resin curing systems is mainly concerned with the resin gel-time which is critical to the wrap processing. In general, cold setting resin systems (ambient temperature curing) should be used in this wet lay-up processing, because of the large scale and the open site condition in practical applications. Since the machine lay-up is not easy to be carried out in the wrapping process described in this study, the hand lay-up method was applied.

Figure 1 Concrete column wrapped by glass fibre composites

Specimens Preparation

The concrete columns were produced following the Standards Association of Australia. The columns were 300 mm high and 150 mm in the diameter using a weight mixture ratio of 1:1.4:2.3:5 (water:cement:sand:aggregate). The concrete cylinders were compacted, capped, and cured for 28 days before the tests, with an average compressive strength of 48 MPa. The surface of the concrete columns was sanded using 40# sand paper. The composite wrap types and architectures are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Details of composite architectures used for wrapping concrete columns

Type	Details of wraps architecture
A	3 layers of WR (600 g/m ² *)
B	3 layers of WR/CSM (900 g/m ²)
C	2 layers of GFT (250 g/m ²)
D	3 layers of WR/CSM (900 g/m ²) + 2 layers of GFT

* Unit weigh of each layer

The concrete columns were wrapped using a brush and a consolidating roller. The vinyl-ester resin was mixed with 1.5% of the normal reaction MEKP catalyst at ambient temperature. Before laying the first layer, a resin coat was applied to seal micro holes on the surface of concrete columns, then each layer was wetted and rolled on to the concrete columns to ensure full consolidation. The weight ratio of glass fibre to resin for types A and type B are 1:1 and 1:1.3 respectively; 1:0.85 and 1:1.24 for types C and D respectively.

Mechanical Testing

All compression tests for the columns were conducted following the standard of AS 1012.9-1986 (Method for the Determination of the Compressive Strength of Concrete Specimens), performed on a DARTC testing machine which has a maximum axial compressive loading capacity of 2000 kN. The tests were conducted at a constant cross-head speed of 0.021 mm/s (0.05 in/min). The axial deformation data were collected using three LVDT (Liner Voltage Displacement Transducer) transducers, arranged in a circle of 120° between each other. All data of tests were continually recorded using a computer data acquisition system every 3 seconds. For each type of composite wrapped concrete columns, five specimens were tested, and the average results are presented in the following discussion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the typical global responses of the concrete columns wrapped with various composite architectures subjected to compressive loading. The results of compression tests of all the columns are summarised in Tables 2 and 3 respectively. The increase percentage was calculated as

$$\text{Efficiency \%} = \{(\text{Reinforced}-\text{Unreinforced})/\text{Unreinforced}\} \times 100.$$

The structural stiffnesses of all columns, in terms of the initial slope of the load-deformation curve, are given in Table 4.

Figure 2 Typical global responses of concrete columns wrapped with various composite architectures

Table 2 Strengthening efficiency of concrete columns with different composite wraps

Type	Total Glass Content [g/m ²]	Average Load at Failure [kN]	Standard Deviation [kN]	Efficiency in Load [%]
Concrete	---	856	32	---
Type A	1800	1167	39	36
Type B	2700	1373	56	60
Type C	500	910	31	6
Type D	3200	1574	54	83

Table 3 Axial deformation of concrete columns with different composite wraps

Type	Average Deformation at Failure [mm]	Standard Deviation of Deformation [mm]	Efficiency in Deformation [%]
Concrete	1.43	0.10	---
Type A	3.77	0.58	164
Type B	5.77	0.37	303
Type C	2.52	0.17	76
Type D	6.01	0.01	320

Table 4 Structural stiffness of concrete columns with different composite wraps

Type	E [GPa]
Concrete	12.6 ± 1.6
Type A	14.6 ± 0.9
Type B	14.2 ± 0.7
Type C	13.1 ± 0.7
Type D	15.6 ± 0.5

It was found that duplication of glass fabric layers from 2 to 4 significantly increased the load-carrying capacity, but did not change the deformation characteristics[2], shown in Table 5. However, in this study, adding chopped strand mat (300g/m²) into woven roving layers (Type B), the experimental results have shown that there are clearly increments in both load-carrying capacity and deformation capability, compared to those of Type A (Figure 1 and Table 5).

It is interesting to see that Type C wrap with only two layers of GFT provides a confinement to the concrete column and produces a significantly increase in deformation capability. However, it does not give an effectively enhancement in the load-carrying capacity, with only 6% of the increment. But when two layers of GFT wraps were applied in Type D, a clear increase in the load-carrying capacity, with 23% of the increment above Type B, is achieved (Figure 1 and Table 2).

Table 5 Comparison of reinforcing efficiency of WR and CSM/WR architectures

No	Type	Fibre content [g/m ²]	Average load at failure [kN]	Deformation at failure [mm]
1	2 layers roving cloth (800g/m ²)[2]	1600	1023.9	2.95
2	4 layers roving cloth (800g/m ²)[2]	3200	1352.3	2.93
3	3 layers of WR (600g/m ²)	1800	1167.2	3.77
4	3 layers of WR/CSM (900g/m ²)	2700	1371.3	5.77

Figure 3 Failure appearance of concrete columns with various composite wrapping architectures

The post failure appearance of the concrete columns wrapped with various composite architectures is shown in Figure 3. The composite jackets create a high degree of confinement to the concrete columns, meanwhile it can be seen that the failure pattern of WR on the surface of Type A composite jacket shows a brittle failure, but Type B exhibits more fibre bundle pulling failure on the surface of the WR/CSM composite jacket. However, there is not much fibre bundle pulling failure on the surface of Type D, because of the “tightening up” efficiency of the two layers of GFT as the out layers.

Since carbon and kevlar fibres are expensive, the E-glass fibre is applied in this study to match the strengthening efficiency by increasing the thickness of the composite jacket. Using the lay-up of WR/CSM, the high bonding efficiency between layers of WR can be obtained. Moreover, this type of architecture is suitable for the hand lay-up to squeeze out air bubbles. Depending on the scale of the subjects, the combined method of the machine resin wetting/hand lay-up may be applied to many cases of repair and rehabilitation of civil infrastructure using the system introduced in this study.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite Element Model (FEM)

The concrete columns in this study can be assumed to be solid cylinders wrapped with a composites shell which is perfectly bonded to the concrete[7]. Due to the axial symmetry, a two dimension model can be applied to carry out stress analysis using ABAQUS finite element package. The FEM mesh consists of 18 elements in the radial direction and 100 elements in the axial direction, shown in Figure 4. In the evaluations, the concrete and composite jacket were considered as isotropic materials, being perfect elastic-plastic and linear-elastic, respectively.

The mechanical properties of the concrete and composite (Type B) are given in Table 6. Young’s modulus and compressive strength of the concrete were determined from the compressive tests of concrete columns, and those for the composite were determined form tensile tests using coupon specimens.

Table 6 Material properties of concrete and composite

Type	Elastic Modulus [GPa]	Poisson Ratio	Compression Strength [MPa]	Tension Strength [MPa]
Concrete	12.6	0.1 [8]	48	---
Type B	14.2	0.26 [8]	---	210

Figure 4 Mesh pattern for concrete column wrapped with composites shell

Figure 5 Comparison of FEM evaluation and experimental data for columns with Type B wraps

Load-Deformation Response

The experimental load-deformation curves (Figure 5) illustrate that the initial response is almost linear up to a yield point (kink point). The concrete began to fail beyond this point, and the curves continue almost in a linear manner with a reduced slope, with the composite wrap holding the concrete column together. Catastrophic failure occurred when the composite wrap bursted (failure point). The deformation at the failure point is a measure of the ductility of the wrapped concrete columns. The curve of FEM shows a good agreement with experimental results.

Both Young's modulus and thickness of the composite jacket can be taken as variables to identify the stiffening mechanisms of the composite jackets. Assuming the yielding strength of the concrete is 48 MPa with Young's modulus of 12.6 GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.1, the

reinforcing efficiency of composite jackets with various composite moduli and thicknesses was evaluated for the case as follows.

- 1) the thickness of the composite jacket was assumed to be a constant ($T=3.6$ mm) and Young's modulus was enlarged from 10 GPa to 30 GPa; and
- 2) Young's modulus was assumed to be a constant ($E=15$ GPa) and the thickness was increased from 2.4 mm to 4.8 mm.

Figures 6 and 7 show effects of Young's modulus and thickness of composite jackets on the kink stress and load-deformation responses of the composite wrapped concrete columns. It can be seen that the increase of Young's modulus of the composite jackets results in increments in the kink stress, leading to higher axial stresses when the concrete fails, and significant increments in the slope of the load-deformation curve after the kink point. These results can also be achieved through the alternation of the thickness of the composite jackets.

Figure 6 Effect of Young's modulus of composite jacket on kink stress

Figure 7 Effect of thickness of composite jacket on kink stress

Effect of loading condition

A finite element model was developed to examine the effect of loading conditions on the responses of the composite wrapped concrete columns. Shown in Figure 9, the curve A with the axial stress applied only to the concrete has a higher kink stress than curve B with the axial stress applied to both concrete and composite jacket. This result shows that if the top and bottom ends of the composite jacket are not subjected to the compressive load directly, the composite jacket can produce a higher strengthening efficiency to the concrete column.

Figure 9 Effect of loading conditions on response of composite wrapped concrete column (Type B)

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the experimental studies and the finite element analyses, the following points can be concluded:

- 1) The use of E-glass fibres and the vinyl-ester resin to reinforce concrete columns externally is effective, with a lower cost of raw materials.
- 2) The reinforcing efficiency is highly dependent on the composite architecture, with a hybrid system of roving cloth, chopped strand mat, and glass fibre tape showing highest enhancement; and
- 3) The FEM analysis can be used to tailor the design of the composite jackets.

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